

Exploring the Influence of Gender and Profession on Perceptions of Technology: A Multidimensional Analysis

Dr.P.Preeti¹, Syed Shoaib Ali²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, Lords Institute of Engineering and Technology
MBA 1st Years,

²Department of Management Studies, Lords Institute of Engineering and Technology

Corresponding Author – Dr.P.Preeti

Email: preethi.hr13@gmail.com

Abstract:

Technology has transformed living, learning, working, and communicating. Rapid technological advancement has transformed life. Technology's ease, efficiency, connection, privacy, cyber threats, and technological unemployment are highlighted. Technology has changed everything about human life and the world in ways we never dreamed decades ago. This article explores the complex and ever-changing relationship between technology and humans, including its merits and downsides. This study examines how gender, employment, and technology perceptions impact technology attitudes across industries. Hypothesis testing reveals gender does not alter technical attitudes. The report promotes gender-sensitive and gender-neutral technology design and education. It also proposes targeting profession-specific issues and doing further study. These findings show the need for sophisticated strategies to encourage inclusive and ethical technology use across diverse groups and professions.

Keywords: Gender, Profession, Technology Perceptions, Technology Adoption, Inclusivity, Technology Use, Risk Perception

Introduction:

Scientists create technology to attain goals. Technology has changed life, work, and communication. Technology has changed healthcare, education, transportation, and entertainment. Technology was created through curiosity, invention, and life improvement. Rapid technological innovation transforms communication and boosts growth. Technology affects life, work, and communication. We achieved online collaboration, new communities, and global knowledge. The workplace changed with technology. Remote and online jobs foster global collaboration. Technology has an impact on many aspects of our lives. Understanding technology perspectives is crucial for equitable integration. We assess the value, danger, information intake, gender, and job aspects of technology. Examine how gender and job influence technology views in a subtle but critical way. This study suggests that professional environments, gender-sensitive technology design, and education may encourage responsible and inclusive technology usage across demographics and professions.

Research Methodology:

The purpose:

This goal of this study is to investigate the impact of several factors, including gender, employment, and attitudes towards technology, on many outcome variables pertaining to the effect and consequences of technology on society and daily existence.

1. Research Design: This study utilizes a statistical approach to examine the effects of technology on

different facets of human life. The research covers descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and multivariate analysis.

2. Data Collection:

Population and Sample: The study will target a diverse population that includes different genders and professions. A sample of at least 112 respondents were been collected through an online survey. Data were collected through a survey with respondents answering questions related to their demographics (e.g., Gender, Profession) and their perceptions of technology's impact on different aspects of life (e.g., thinking processes, usefulness, information consumption, societal dependence, positive impacts, work/school life, side effects, and risks).

Survey Instrument: A structured questionnaire will be developed to collect data on the following variables:

3. Hypothesis Statements:

Hypothesis Statements

- **H₁:** A robust correlation exists between gender and the conviction that technology influences our thought processes and thought patterns.
- **H₂:** A strong a connection exists between gender systems and the sense of technology's use in daily life.
- **H₃:** There is a strong correlation between sexual orientation and the viewpoint of how technology impacts the manner in which we consume and distribute information.
- **H₄:** There is a strong correlation across gender roles and the thoughts of hazards connected with utilizing technology

- **H₅**: There is an association between profession and the perception of whether technology is useful in life.
- **H₆**: There is an association between profession and the perception of whether technology is useful in life.
- **H₇**: There is an association between profession and the perception of how technology influences the way we consume and share information.
- **H₈**: There is an association between profession and the perception of risks associated with using technology.

4. Data Analysis:

Descriptive Statistics:

For the purpose of providing a concise summary of the data, descriptive statistics will be

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.673	6

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS

Interpretation: The 6 items in the study had a satisfactory level of internal consistency, as shown

produced. These statistics will include the means, standard deviations, and frequencies for categorical variables.

Variables:

Dependent Variables: Perception of Technology's Impact on Thinking Processes, Usefulness of Technology in Life, Impact on Information Consumption and Sharing, Risks Associated with Technology

Independent Variables: Gender and Profession

Chi Square Test :

Dependent Variables: Tech influenced the way we think and process, Is technology useful in life, Tech influenced the way we consume and share information, Risks associated with using technology

Independent Variables: Gender

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Range	Mean	Std. Deviation	Kurtosis	Std. Error
Gender	111	2	1.5	0.537	-1.144	0.455
Profession	111	1	1.29	0.455	-1.123	0.455
Tech influenced the way we think and process	111	2	1.57	0.683	-0.513	0.455
Is technology useful in life	111	3	1.53	0.685	0.656	0.455
Tech influenced the way we consume and share information	111	2	1.51	0.773	-0.424	0.455
Risks associated with using technology	111	2	1.61	0.811	-0.975	0.455

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS.

Interpretation:

The mean values indicate generally positive perceptions of technology's impact on various aspects of life. The standard deviations suggest moderate variability, meaning there are differences in individual perceptions but not extremely wide variations. Kurtosis values vary, with some variables showing flat distributions and others indicating peaked distributions, suggesting

differences in how perceptions are distributed across respondents. The standard errors of kurtosis suggest reliable measurements of the shape of the distributions.

Taking into account both the fundamental patterns and the variety in replies, these findings provide a thorough assessment of the respondents' opinions of the influence that technology has had.

Chi-Square Tests Analysis:

H₁: A robust correlation exists between gender and the conviction that technology influences our thought processes and thought patterns

Table 3: Gender * Tech influenced the way we think and process

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.405 ^a	4	.354
Likelihood Ratio	4.127	4	.389
Linear-by-Linear Association	.100	1	.752
N of Valid Cases	111		

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS**

Interpretation: Given that the p-value (0.354) is more than the threshold of 0.05, it is not feasible for us to reject the null hypothesis for the reasons stated above. The fact that this is the case suggests that there is no statistically significant connection

between gender and the sense of how technology alters the manner in which we think and process information. In light of the fact that the null hypothesis is false, it may be concluded that this link does not exist.

H₂: A strong a connection exists between gender systems and the sense of technology's use in daily life.

Table 4: Gender * Is technology useful in life

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.289 ^a	6	.507
Likelihood Ratio	6.514	6	0.368
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.524	1	0.217
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS**

Interpretation: With a p-value of 0.507, we are unable to reject the null hypothesis, which indicates

that there is no significant connection involving sexual orientation and one's opinion of the utility of technology in life.

H₃: There is a strong correlation between sexual orientation and the viewpoint of how technology impacts the manner in which we consume and distribute information

Table 5: Gender * Tech influenced the way we consume and share information

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.693 ^a	4	.610
Likelihood Ratio	2.596	4	.627
Linear-by-Linear Association	.265	1	.607
N of Valid Cases	111		

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS**

Interpretation: As a result of the fact that the p-value is 0.610, it is possible to draw the conclusion that there is no statistically significant association between genders and the manner in which

technology influences the way in which we acquire and disseminate information.

H₄: There is a strong correlation across gender roles and the thoughts of hazards connected with utilizing technology

Table 6: Gender * Risks associated with using technology

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.501 ^a	4	.644
Likelihood Ratio	3.215	4	.522
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.905	1	.168
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.3 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS**

Interpretation: With a p-value of 0.644, it is possible to draw the conclusion that there is not a

statistically significant connection between one's race and their assessment of the risks associated with the use of technology.

H₅: There is an association between profession and the perception of whether technology is useful in life

Table 7: Profession * Tech influenced the way we think and process

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.576 ^a	2	.167
Likelihood Ratio	3.363	2	.186
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.212	1	.073
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.1 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .946. Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS

Interpretation: We are unable to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value (0.167) is more than the threshold of 0.05, which is the level of significance that we have set. The conclusion that can be drawn from this is that there is no statistically significant connection between one's employment and their impression of how technology alters the method in

which knowledge is processed and thought about. The evidence presented here demonstrates, on the contrary, that there is no positive association between the two.

H₆: There is an association between profession and the perception of whether technology is useful in life.

Table 8: Profession *Is technology useful in life

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.805 ^a	3	.008
Likelihood Ratio	10.842	3	.013
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.571	1	.033
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.3 cells (37.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .29.

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS”

Interpretation: We conclude that the null hypothesis is not true since the p-value is 0.008. In

light of this, it seems that there is a statistically significant connection between one's career and their assessment of the usefulness of technology in everyday life.

H₇: There is an association between profession and the perception of how technology influences the way we consume and share information.

Table 9: Profession * Tech influenced the way we consume and share information

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.319 ^a	2	.190
Likelihood Ratio	3.225	2	.199
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.169	1	.075
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.48.

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS”

Interpretation: There is no significant link between occupation and an understanding of how technology

impacts the way we consume and distribute information, as shown by the p-value of 0.190, which shows that there is currently no such association.

H₈: There is an association between profession and the perception of risks associated with using technology.

Table 10: Profession * Risks associated with using technology

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.706 ^a	2	.021
Likelihood Ratio	7.166	2	.028
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.895	1	.015
N of Valid Cases	111		

a.0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.34.

Source: Data collected from survey respondents regarding the impact of technology on various aspects of human life. Analyzed using SPSS”

Interpretation: We conclude that the null hypothesis is not true since the p-value is 0.021. According to this, there seems to be a statistically significant connection between one's career and

Suggestions:

- Future research could delve deeper into gender-neutral approaches in technology design and education to ensure inclusivity and diversity in addressing cognitive impacts.
- It is necessary to investigate gender-sensitive methods in the adoption and implementation of technology in order to address the varied demands and preferences of users.
- Highlighting inclusive channels for exchanging information and implementing initiatives to improve digital literacy might promote the inclusion of varied gender views in the usage of technology.
- Developing risk communication tactics that take into account gender differences might effectively address concerns and encourage responsible technology usage among various user groups.
- Investigating specialized training programs and cognitive therapies might help address different views of technology among different job sectors.
- Customized professional development programs and industry-specific strategies may optimize the efficacy of technology in different professional settings.
- Promoting interdisciplinary cooperation frameworks may facilitate the sharing of innovative information across diverse professional domains.
- By incorporating risk mitigation strategies and technological governance frameworks that are tailored to certain industries, professionals may effectively tackle the unique difficulties they face.

Conclusion

This research investigates the intricate relationship between gender, profession, and attitudes towards technology, revealing nuanced and comprehensive conclusions. The occupation one holds has a substantial impact on how they see technology, especially in regards to its use and potential threats. Conversely, gender does not have a substantial influence on these judgments. These results highlight the importance of considering work

their opinion of the dangers that are linked with the use of technology.

circumstances when examining attitudes towards technology. Additionally, they highlight the need of tailored strategies for implementing technology and creating policies. By recognizing the diverse effects of gender and vocation, stakeholders may formulate more accurate approaches to encourage inclusive and responsible use of technology across various demographics and professional domains.

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